

ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN NON- PHILOLOGICAL DEPARTMENTS

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Absrtact: Effective communication skills are essential for success in any professional field, including non-philological departments. This abstract explores the importance of developing communicative skills among students in non-philological disciplines and highlights key strategies to enhance their verbal and written communication abilities. By focusing on clear expression, active listening, and interpersonal communication skills, students can improve their professional capabilities, build strong relationships, and excel in diverse work environments. Investing in the development of communicative skills can lead to increased productivity, improved collaboration, and greater career opportunities for students in non-philological departments.

Keywords: Communication skills, non-native speakers, management students, vocabulary, professional communication, institution, non-philological department, verbal.

Introduction. In today's interconnected world, effective communication skills are essential for success in any field. While communication skills are often emphasized in philological departments, they are equally important in non-philological departments. Developing strong communicative skills can help individuals in various disciplines excel in their careers, build relationships, and navigate complex professional environments.

In the realm of academia and professional settings, the importance of

effective communication cannot be overstated. While often associated with fields such as linguistics and literature, the need for strong communicative skills is equally vital in non-philological departments. Whether in STEM disciplines, business environments, healthcare sectors, or beyond, the ability to convey information clearly, engage in productive dialogue, and collaborate effectively is essential for success.

This introduction sets the stage for exploring the significance of enhancing communicative skills within non-philological departments. By recognizing the universal value of proficient communication across various academic and professional domains, we can delve into strategies and practices aimed at equipping students and professionals with the necessary tools to excel in their respective fields. Strengthening communicative abilities not only enhances individual performance but also promotes better teamwork, problem-solving, and overall success in diverse organizational settings.

Literature review: As N.N.Normatova states, "The process of developing the oral speech skills of foreign language for linguistic departments of Higher Education is different from the process of developing it for non-philological departments. The process has its own peculiarities. The quality of education, which is a bilateral process between the teacher and student, depends on the didactic perfection of teacher`s mastery, and on the other hand, the on the student's motivational activity. Meanwhile, if the high scientific potential and methodological skills of the teacher is integrated with the educational activity of students high results can be achieved in the short term period"[5;97].

From the point of view of N.M. Akramova:” Modern professionally oriented training is aimed at mastering the language as a means of communication within the chosen profession. In this case, the foreign language is a means of increasing communicative competence and personal and professional development of students and is a prerequisite for the successful professional activity of a specialist

graduate of a modern higher school, able to conduct business contacts with foreign partners. However, the success of verbal communication depends not only on the speaker's desire to come into contact, but also on the ability to realize his or her verbal intention, which depends on the degree of knowledge of language units and the ability to use them in specific situations of communication ”[2,120].

It is important for today's specialist to be able to communicate effectively in his work in order to meet international standards, be competent and competitive. During the years of independence, special attention has been paid to language education in our country, in particular, to the sectorial study of professional communication in foreign languages. One of our current problems is the lack of a culture of professional communication in any foreign language by employees in the field of management, as well as representatives of industry, economy, tourism, banking, education and other fields. In this regard, the organization of language training of management students in a career-oriented manner, the development of professional communication skills of future professionals is of great scientific and practical importance [3,59].

Methods. We all know that training students to speak a foreign language fluently is the primary goal of professional communication development and instruction. Foreign language proficiency is required for communication in technical higher education institutions, where learning a foreign language is a practical objective that requires vocabulary mastery. Without being able to speak, write, listen, or comprehend the language, they are illiterate. Acquiring vocabulary in a language broadens pupils' perspectives and increases their subject-matter expertise.

One of the main tasks facing students aiming to learn foreign languages in non-philological institutions of higher education this year is that this year's pedagogical experience has shown that the basic qualities of receptive lexical skills (skills, abilities) are not well formed in students. Although the quality of

foreign language teaching has improved significantly in recent years, teaching this subject poses certain challenges [3,65].

As an example, we can cite students' poor mastery of vocabulary. Students do not have enough vocabulary to make professional communication, they do not know how to spell or translate simple words, cannot pronounce them correctly, and so on.

Therefore, we think that these issues will be resolved and useful assistance will be given in teaching a foreign language if students in non-philological schools are permitted to work with specialist words depending on their chosen profession. Students will be able to speak texts and technical instructions, and we believe they will have no trouble understanding the structures for correct usage. Gaining proficiency in vocabulary linked to the field in English helps students in non-philological higher education institutions become more independent workers and expand their knowledge base.

a) teaching field terms to develop professional communication in English in non-philological higher education institutions;

b) insufficient availability of textbooks in non-philological higher education institutions that provide teaching of field terms and glossaries;

c) lack of scientific study of the development of field terms and methods of field texts in non-philological higher education institutions;

d) the special role of technology in the specialization of terms by students to speak fluently in the language being studied.

The above issues are not yet well addressed in the methodology of teaching English in non-philological institutions of higher education, so we consider the development of professional communication of students in English classes in non-philological institutions and the teaching of relevant terms is one of the most pressing issues today.

In order to develop professional communication in English, a methodology

for teaching and using relevant terms in speech must be developed. This methodology should be based on an analysis of language experience, linguo-didactical bases of foreign language teaching, and psychological characteristics of students in non-philological institutions. The method of teaching English terms, words, and phrases to students of non-philological institutes and universities is an important factor, taking into consideration the conditions of non-philological higher education institutions. In non-philological higher education institutions, terminology are created specifically for the purpose of teaching methodological guides, textbooks, and developing professional communication skills in a foreign language for management students [4,80].

Results and Discussion. Study and evaluation of current pedagogical, psychological, and methodological literature as well as field textbooks and guides for students majoring in management of non-philological higher education institutions; study of educational institution documents; focused observation of foreign language instruction; lesson analysis and comparative approach based on IT advancements; conducting surveys and interviews; experimental testing; test; an approach within the framework of the suggestions and conclusions of lexical teaching methodological manuals and mathematical statistics.

It consists of the following Methods:

- Development of developed requirements for electronic and educational terminological dictionary of terms in the field of development of professional communication of foreign languages of management students in non-philological higher education institutions;

- To determine the conditions for students of management to learn industry terms in the implementation of professional communication skills;

- Development and implementation of methodological recommendations for the development of professional skills of management students in the field of foreign language. Management of non-philological institutions provides a

methodology for the use of auxiliary literature in the field of technical terms in foreign language classes, as well as active communication in foreign language professional activities for students of Uzbek and Russian groups studying in non-philological institutions. selective demonstration of phraseology and practical-creative methods and scientific-theoretical recommendations to overcome the difficulties in teaching technical terms.

A foreign language is considered in terms of the relationship between the development of professional communication and a systematic approach to the teaching of text, dialogue, vocabulary and terminology related to the field.

There will be the development of both theoretical and practical methods for learning technical subjects in English. The first organized explanatory dictionaries were crucial to the development of English lexicography and the understanding of English vocabulary. The lexicon of a language can be studied with great benefit via the following dictionaries: etymological, word-forming, orthographic, phraseological, synonym, antonym, and homonym, among others. Uzbek and Russian lexicographies are growing alongside lexicographies of foreign languages, and the release of an elucidating dictionary for the Uzbek language will be crucial to expanding the vocabularies of both languages.

It is known that employees of industrial and economic management communicate in Uzbek, Russian and English during their service.

Therefore, the main novelty of this work is to help develop a culture of professional communication in a foreign language by demonstrating the basic terms used in management and economics as well as business and working on texts in their study. Here is the diagram which indicates the level of understanding of English among management students:

Understanding of English among management students

Now in Uzbekistan, knowledge of English and Russian, along with the native language, is a great help in the field of specialization and expands the study of achievements in the field. Due to the fact that most of the professional information comes in Russian and English, today the priority for the specialist is to know these languages, to get the necessary information from English-language information, text and communication.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, developing communicative skills is vital for success in non-philological departments. By focusing on clear verbal and written communication, active listening, and interpersonal skills, individuals can enhance their professional capabilities, build strong relationships, and thrive in diverse work environments. Investing in the development of communicative skills can lead to increased productivity, improved collaboration, and greater career opportunities in any field.

The development of professional communication is called the difficulties in translating terms related to the field, and it shows the method of students' independent work with vocabulary. In the implementation of professional communication, the teaching of sectoral textbooks, manuals, relevant texts and

terms in a foreign language is associated with the gradual implementation of their skills, as well as the teaching of translation of words and phrases. In nonphilological higher education institutions, it is important to teach management terms and develop communication skills in management students.

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